

An agroecological assessment of UAV spraying in Greek viticulture

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Abstract

UAV spraying in Europe is constrained by regulation despite this technology's potential to reduce the impact of pesticide use on the environment and human health. The implications of current EU regulation were investigated by modelling UAV spraying in Greek viticulture. Profitability of UAV spraying was 6% and 5% lower than conventional spraying on a flat and a steep-slope vineyard, respectively. UAV spraying did not decrease environmental risk of pesticide use, but human exposure to pesticides was 50% to 67% lower. Farmers prioritising economic or environmental goals preferred ground spraying while socially-orientated farmers obtained a higher satisfaction when adopting UAV spraying.

Keywords: Regulation, Profitability, Environmental risk, Pesticide exposure, Multi-criteria

Introduction

Viticulture is a valuable segment of the European rural economy (Chen *et al.*, 2022). Today, this sector is challenged by factors such as pesticide resistance, labour scarcity, increasing production costs, declining wine consumption and climate change (Chen *et al.*, 2022; DG AGRI, 2023). These challenges have led to vineyard abandonment across multiple European regions (Perpiña Castillo *et al.*, 2018). In this context, the adoption of technology such as UAVs is expected to maintain or improve profitability while reducing the impact on the environment and human health.

UAV systems include three components: a UAV, a ground-based controller, and a communications system (Morales-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2022). They have been employed in agriculture for applying inputs such as fertilisers and pesticides, gradually replacing crewed aircraft (Morales-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2022; OECD, 2021; Poss *et al.*, 2023). UAVs are advantageous in wet soil conditions, small and irregularly shaped fields and unfavourable topography (Ozkan, 2024; Poss *et al.*, 2023). Applying chemical inputs with a UAV can also be beneficial for farm operators' health and safety, especially for those using hose or backpack sprayers (Ozkan, 2024; Poss *et al.*, 2023). However, European farmers and farm contractors are unable to exploit these opportunities due to regulation banning most aerial pesticide spraying. This is despite the potential of UAV technology for helping to meet the EU objective to halve pesticide use and risk by 2030.

Regulation of UAVs in Europe is complex and their manufacturing requirements and operational use are responsibility of multiple authorities. Based on Regulation (EU) 2019/947, spray UAVs fall in the certified UAV category because they carry pesticides, which are considered as dangerous goods (European Commission, 2019b). Operating a

UAV in agriculture is governed by Directive 2009/128/EC, which prohibits aerial spraying. However, Art. 9 of Directive 2009/128/EC allows for derogations if there are no viable alternatives or there is an advantage “in terms of reduced impacts on human health and the environment compared with land-based application of pesticides” (European Parliament and European Council, 2009: p.8). In some Member States, exceptional permissions for UAV spraying have been allowed in recent years. Nevertheless, these permissions are costly, time-consuming and are granted on a crop-by-crop and chemical-by-chemical basis, thereby limiting UAV spraying adoption in Europe. Additionally, Directive 2009/128/EC mandates that UAVs must be equipped with the best available technology to reduce spray drift (European Parliament and European Council, 2009), which may reduce pesticide efficacy and promote resistance development for certain crops and active substances (OECD, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2019).

This study investigated the economic, environmental and social implications of UAV spraying regulation in Europe by modelling a flat and a steep-slope vineyard located in Greece. Farmer utility, commonly referred to as satisfaction, was measured for three decision-maker typologies placing different levels of importance on three farm-level goals. The goals included gross economic return, environmental impact, and operators’ risk of exposure to pesticides. These were assessed for conventional ground spraying and UAV spraying and compared to identify strengths and weaknesses of UAV use. The hypotheses of this study were that: (i) UAV spraying is less profitable than using a conventional vine sprayer but more profitable than backpack spraying; (ii) at ground equipment pesticide rates, the environmental impact of UAV spraying is comparable to land-based application of pesticides; and (iii) UAV spraying reduces the risk of human exposure to pesticides. The first hypothesis was tested because, regardless of the agroecological performance of an innovative technology, economic feasibility is a prerequisite to farm survival (Ewert *et al.*, 2023). The second and third hypotheses were relevant to the requirements of UAV spraying to reduce the impact of pesticide use on the environment and human health to be granted permission under EU regulation (European Parliament and European Council, 2009). The latter were particularly important on flat vineyards, where well-established and viable pesticide spraying alternatives might make it more difficult to obtain UAV spraying permissions.

Materials and methods

The Hands-Free Hectare multi-objective linear programming model

This research used the Hands-Free Hectare multi-objective linear programming (HFH-MOLP) model to estimate three farm-level goals for three decision-maker types motivated by different priorities. The HFH-MOLP model is a decision-making support tool capable of estimating farmer satisfaction in situations of conflicting economic, ecological and social objectives based on the deviation from desired or undesired farm-level goals. It is an extension of the Hands-Free Hectare linear programming model described in Lowenberg-DeBoer *et al.* (2021). The HFH-MOLP model was run in the general algebraic modelling system (GAMS Development Corporation, 2023).

Model goals and decision-maker types

The farm goals were gross return, environmental impact and human exposure to pesticides. Each goal was used to quantify a specific objective using the following equation:

$$\min G = w_1 \left(\frac{G_1^-}{G_{opt}^-} \right) + w_2 \left(1 - \frac{G_2^-}{G_{wrs}^2} \right) + w_3 \left(1 - \frac{G_3^-}{G_{wrs}^3} \right) \quad (1)$$

where, G was the target variable to be minimised, representing the loss of farmer satisfaction incurred when objectives were not fully met; w_1 , w_2 and w_3 were weights respectively assigned to the economic, ecological and social objectives to simulate farmer priorities; G_1^- , G_2^- and G_3^- were variables quantifying the negative deviation from desired or undesired goals; and G_{opt}^- , G_{wrs}^2 and G_{wrs}^3 were the desired or undesired goals used to normalise objectives achievement.

The above equation indicates that a hypothetical farmer aims to maximise the economic goal while minimising environmental impact and human exposure to pesticides. The modelled decision-maker types were a production-orientated ($w_1 = 100\%$, $w_2 = w_3 = 0\%$), an ecologically-orientated ($w_1 = 70\%$, $w_2 = 30\%$, $w_3 = 0\%$), and a socially-orientated farmer ($w_1 = 70\%$, $w_2 = 0\%$, $w_3 = 30\%$). A 30%-weight was considered as a reasonable value to represent non-economic priorities while ensuring farm business viability.

Economic objective

The economic objective was measured via farm gross return by deducting variable costs from the sum of sales revenue and EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) payments. Variable costs included fertilisers, pesticides, fuel, and hiring fees for an UAV and a grapes harvester when harvesting was not manual. Variable costs also included wages for temporary workers that could be hired during peak times. Two workers per month were assumed to be available. CAP payments included available payments in Greece. Gross return excluded farm operator labour, management, risk taking and fixed costs. Farm operator labour and management were excluded because the two modelled vineyards were assumed to be family-run and family labour is generally compensated out of profits in small farm businesses (Vollmer and Schwarz, 2003). Risk was modelled using the good field days approach described in Lowenberg-DeBoer *et al.* (2021). Fixed costs were excluded to focus the analysis on vineyard profitability in the short term.

Ecological and social objectives

The two non-economic objectives were measured following the pesticide load indicator (PLI) developed by the Danish Environmental Protection Agency (2012) and used to quantify pesticide tax in Denmark. More details on the PLI can be found in Kudsk *et al.* (2018). To fit in the HFH-MOLP model, the PLI methodology was broken down into four unitless indicators corresponding to selected model goals and sub-goals. Higher indicator values represented greater impact on the parameter under consideration. The pesticide load (PL) for human health (PL_{hh}) was isolated from the PLI methodology to quantify the human exposure to pesticides goal (i.e., the social objective). Exposure factors for UAV and backpack spraying were assumed to be 0.5 and 1.5, respectively. These values considered pesticide exposure risk variability as a result of pesticide form (i.e., powder, liquid or solid) and mode of application. The ecological objective was expressed as the mean of three sub-goals: biodiversity loss, soil health reduction and water pollution. Biodiversity loss was set equal to the mean of pesticides bio-concentration risk in off-target species and the PLI for ecotoxicology (PL_{eco}). Soil health reduction corresponded to risk of pesticides persistence in soil using active substance half-life values. Water

pollution was calculated as the mean of pesticide surface and groundwater mobilities based on Freundlich soil-water partition coefficients and groundwater ubiquity scores.

Tested scenarios

This analysis simulated 4 scenarios (2 vineyard types x 2 pesticide spraying strategies) (Table 1). The first vineyard was a flat vineyard located in Attica, the most commercially important viticultural region of Central Greece (Lazarakis, 2018). On this vineyard, the majority of farm operations were assumed to be mechanised. The vineyard had an area of 8 ha. The second vineyard was located in Crete, where steep-slope viticulture is common (Lazarakis, 2018). Most farm operations on the steep-slope vineyard were assumed to be manual owing to its topography. This vineyard had an area of 3 ha. Both vineyards were assumed to grow a mixture of white and red varieties for direct sale (i.e., no winemaking). Vines were trained with a vertical shoot positioning system. The scenarios assumed that disease pressure was sufficiently low to make UAV spraying as efficacious as ground spraying based on Dubuis and Jaquerod (2022). High disease pressure scenarios requiring additional ground spraying after UAV treatments will be tested in further research.

Table 1. The four scenarios included in this study

Vineyard type	Pesticide spraying strategy	Scenario
Flat vineyard (8 ha)	Vine sprayer	1-A
	UAV aerial broadcast	1-B
Steep-slope vineyard (3 ha)	Backpack sprayer	2-A
	UAV aerial broadcast	2-B

Pesticide treatments included two strategies: (i) conventional spraying, or (ii) UAV aerial broadcast spraying. The conventional sprayers included a 600-litre vine sprayer (Caffini Smart Synthesis Hybrid, Caffini S.P.A., Verona, Italy) on the flat vineyard and a 20-l backpack sprayer on the steep-slope vineyard. The UAV model was assumed to be a XAG P100 (XAG Co. Ltd., Guangzhou, PRC) because of its capacity to produce coarse droplets and a relatively high field efficiency thanks to its 40-l spray tank. The UAV was assumed to cover three vine rows per pass (i.e., working width = 6.6 m) at a speed of 3 m s⁻¹ and at a height of 2 m above the canopy. Spray drift risk of UAV spraying was mitigated by abiding with the weather parameters described in ISO 23117-1:2023. UAV supervision was assumed to be 100% because of visual-line-of-sight rules in Europe. Because aerial spraying is commonly custom-hired (Paraforos, 2024), UAV spraying was assumed to be performed by a contractor at a fee of € 125 ha⁻¹ including labour, pesticide, fuel and setup costs. This fee was equivalent to 50% of the average UAV spraying fee charged in Germany (Paraforos, 2024) to account for lower labour and variable costs in Greece.

Pesticide treatment plan

The vine diseases considered were powdery mildew and downy mildew. This analysis only focused on fungal diseases because they are the main contributors to pesticide use in viticulture (Chen *et al.*, 2022). The fungicide treatment plan included four sprays per year and used mixtures of products registered in Greece. The fungicide products included ARMICARB® 85 SP, DYNALI® 60/30 DC, SERCADIS® 30 SC and SULFOMAT® 80 WG to control powdery mildew and DELAN® PRO 12.5/56.1 SC, FOLPAN® ENERGY, ORONDIS® ULTRA 3/25 SC and ZORVEC VINABEL® 340 SE to treat

against downy mildew. Pesticides were sprayed at a volume of 400 l ha⁻¹ regardless of equipment type to abide with product label requirements.

Results and Discussion

The results of the HFH-MOLP model identified different farmer satisfaction levels across fungicide treatment strategies depending on decision-maker priorities (Table 2). The production-orientated farmer preferred ground spraying equipment on both the flat and the steep-slope vineyard, achieving maximum gross return and consequently 100% satisfaction. Farmer satisfaction levels in the UAV aerial broadcast scenarios were 94% and 95% on the flat and steep-slope vineyard, respectively. A 30% weight on the ecological goals did not change spraying equipment preferences because the environmental impact of UAV aerial broadcast was comparable to land-based spraying, but its profitability was lower. The socially-orientated farmer obtained a satisfaction of 81-87% when adopting UAV aerial broadcast, which in this case was the preferred choice due to a lower risk of workers' exposure to pesticides.

Table 2. Decision-maker satisfaction level by scenario

Scenario	Production-orientated farmer	Ecologically-orientated farmer	Socially-orientated farmer
1-A	100%	70%	70%
1-B	94%	66%	81%
2-A	100%	70%	70%
2-B	95%	67%	87%

Model goal results are provided in Table 3. On the flat vineyard, farm gross return in the UAV spraying scenario was 6% lower compared to using a conventional vine sprayer. Similarly, on the steep-slope vineyard, UAV aerial broadcast led to a 5% reduction in gross return compared to backpack spraying. The short-term profitability of UAV spraying could improve at lower custom-hiring fees, which might become possible if regulation allowed contractors to simultaneously operate multiple UAV units, spray at lower volumes and/or operate at night. For example, in the US, where this practice is more widespread (Erickson and Lowenberg-DeBoer, 2024) and regulation less restrictive (e.g., AgPR, 2024), fees in the range of € 36-71 ha⁻¹ are common (Future Farming, 2024) (€ 1.00 = US\$ 1.05). A sensitivity analysis of the UAV hiring fee assumed for Greek vineyards indicated that a fee of € 42-43 ha⁻¹ would make UAV spraying economically comparable to ground spraying on both vineyards.

Table 3. Model goal results by scenario. Non-economic goals use unitless indicators representing the level of impact of pesticide use on the environment and human health. Higher values indicate a higher impact.

Scenario	Gross return	Biodiversity loss	Soil health reduction	Water pollution	Exposure to pesticides
1-A	€ 49,718	6.89	572.36	98.21	34.98
1-B	€ 46,946	6.89	572.36	98.21	17.49

2-A	€ 21,226	2.40	199.61	34.25	18.30
2-B	€ 20,246	2.40	199.61	34.25	6.10

The hypothesis that UAV spraying would be less profitable than ground sprayers on flat vineyards but more profitable on steep-slope vineyards is rejected. Indeed, steep-slope vineyards would also obtain lower farm gross returns when hiring UAV spraying in current EU regulatory and market conditions. This outcome is dependent on the assumption that family labour is paid out of profits. While on the flat vineyard labour savings in the UAV scenario were close to negligible, 12 farm operator days were saved per year on the steep-slope vineyard when applying pesticide with a UAV. Such substantial labour savings might make UAV spraying more profitable in steep-slope viticulture if vineyards were managed by hired labour rather than family members. Temporary labour was not required in any of the tested scenarios.

UAV spraying was not found to reduce environmental risk because the indicators used in the PLI methodology depend on pesticide inputs per ha. At ground equipment fungicide rates, the environmental impact of UAV spraying was comparable to that of ground equipment, thus corroborating the second hypothesis of this study. The EU objective to halve pesticide use and risk could only be met by reducing pesticide inputs via alternative UAV spraying strategies such as spot-spraying or by allowing UAVs to apply pesticide at lower rates. However, the latter may lead to lower pesticide efficacy and favour resistance development. The risk of human exposure to pesticides of UAV spraying was found to be 50% and 67% lower on the flat and steep-slope vineyard, respectively. This substantial reduction of operators' exposure to pesticides supports the third study hypothesis. These results are highly dependent on the exposure factor values assumed when estimating the PL_{hh} , but are in line with findings by Kuster *et al.* (2023).

Overall, these findings indicate that UAV spraying derogations under Art. 9 of Directive 2009/128/EC on flat vineyards would not be possible if aerial pesticide rates were equivalent to ground spraying because impact of pesticide use on the environment would not be reduced. Besides, flat vineyards would be excluded from this derogation system because of the presence of viable alternatives such as conventional vine spraying. The same would apply to steep-slope viticulture unless vineyards were challenged by severe labour shortages, thereby making backpack spraying impractical due to labour time bottlenecks and potential late pesticide application. Regardless of vineyard topography, UAV spraying would substantially decrease human exposure to pesticides, but this condition is not sufficient to achieve UAV spraying permissions under current regulation. The environmental impact of UAV spraying could be reduced by applying lower pesticide inputs per ha via spot-spraying or other variable-rate approaches. Regardless of its environmental and social performance, UAV spraying would likely face price resistance by potential adopters unless UAV hiring fees were in the range of €40-45 ha⁻¹, similarly to countries like Australia and the US.

Conclusion

This was the first analysis simultaneously focusing on economic, environmental and social implications of UAV spraying regulation in Europe. UAV broadcast spraying in Greek viticulture was found to be less profitable than conventional ground spraying methods and not to reduce the impact of pesticide use on the environment. UAV adoption allowed for improved farm operators' safety, but regulatory barriers are preventing

farmers from exploiting this benefit. Simplification UAV spraying regulation could improve the profitability of this technology in the EU and enable UAV hiring fees comparable to countries such as Australia and the US. Further analysis will assess if economic benefits and decreased environmental impact could be achieved when using lower pesticide inputs via UAV spot-spraying. The effects of higher fungal disease pressure, opportunity cost of family labour on long-term profitability and temporary labour availability will also be assessed.

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